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Online adaptation of the search process of meta-heuristic algorithms

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Abstract:

Due to the high complexity, nonlinear constraints, and interdependencies among variables, most of the real-world optimization/combination problems have a large solution space. This fact, associated to resources and time constraints, make it impossible to implement a deterministic method and evaluate all the possible solutions. Consequently, to get acceptable solutions in a reason amount of time, meta heuristics optimization problems are being used. Generally, metaheuristics are problem agnostic techniques that executes an iterative search process in order to find a near-optimal solution. For this reason, it is being applied to several optimization problems in several different contexts and activity sectors and it have earned more popularity over the deterministic algorithms. However, to obtain good results and a good performance, the metaheuristics must be customized, and a fine-tuning process must be executed on the metaheuristic's parameters. The customization allows the introduction of problem specific knowledge to the algorithm. The parameterization influences the algorithm performance and results by the value of the parameters and by the relation among them. After these processes the algorithm can be come problem tailored and without test it, it is not possible to make sure the same configuration works for other problems. Consequently, before each application, the researchers must start “almost” from scratch, building their own versions. Taking in consideration the high complexity of the new generation of metaheuristics, the time required to optimize metaheuristics is likely to increase in the future. To overcome this, an online parameter adaptation algorithm can be used. This technique consists of to update the metaheuristic parameters dynamically, taking in consideration the current performance and not a training process in a pre-processing phase.

Related References:

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